

FARMER PERCEPTIONS AND DETERMINANTS INFLUENCING THE FARMER PERCEPTION ON CROP ADVISORY IN CHIKKABALLAPUR DISTRICT OF KARNATAKA

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Abstract

Farmers decisions regarding crop advisory services are influenced by multiple factors, including socio-demographic characteristics, farming practices, and external influences as human behaviour of choosing is a mental process which transform perceptions of alternatives into a decision (Van, 2010). This study explores the determinants of farmer perceptions and their willingness to adopt crop advisory systems in three taluks (Chintamani, Chikkaballapur and Gauribidanur) of Chikkaballapur district using a probit model. Primary data collected from 100 sample farmers were analyzed to evaluate the effects of variables such as age, education, gender, and cropping patterns on the adoption of advisory systems. The results reveal that education, gender, and diversified cropping patterns significantly enhance the likelihood of adoption, while age has a negative impact. The findings highlight the need for targeted interventions to address resistance to change and promote advisory services for sustainable agricultural practices.

Key words: Crop advisory, cropping pattern, probit model, sustainability and willingness

Introduction

Crop advisory systems are relevant in assisting the farmers with customized recommendations that are meant to increase productivity, make better use of available resources and respond to the market situations. However, the uptake of such advisory systems was not uniform across regions and farmer demographics. The commercial and subsistence farmers have difference in the decision making of vegetable cultivation (Greig Laura, 2009). Understanding the decision-making process of farmers is essential for extension professionals to develop effective, customized interventions (Russell et al., 2013) and devise strategies that enhance the capabilities of farm managers (Martin, 2017). This study seeks to establish the factors that determine the farmers' perceptions and their willingness to use the crop advisory services in three selected taluks of Chikkaballapur district. With the help of a probit model, the study examines how farmers age, education, and farm size influence these decisions. These insights are essential for policy-making as technological advances do not automatically impair agricultural development, as agricultural extension agencies can intervene and construct measures to overcome obstacles and promote the use of scientific advisory systems.

Methodology

Sample data: The primary data regarding the variables (socio-economic features and other parameters) used for the probit model has been collected by 100 sample farmers from three taluks of Chikkaballapur using a well-structured interview schedule. The taluks under consideration for the study was Chikkaballapur, Chintamani and Gauribidanur.

Probit Analysis: The empirical specification of crop advisory usage choices can be modelled through probit regression analysis. The probit model is a statistical probability model with two categories in the dependent variable (Liao). Probit analysis is based on the cumulative normal probability distribution. The binary dependent variable, y , takes on the values of zero and one. The outcomes of y are mutually exclusive and exhaustive. The dependent variable, y , depends on k observable variables X^k where $k=1, \dots, K$ (Aldrich and Nelson). While the values of zero and one were observed for the dependent variable in the probit model, there was a latent, unobserved continuous variable, y^* .

$$y^* = \sum_{k=1}^K \beta^k X^k + \varepsilon \quad \dots (1)$$

ε is $(0, \sigma^2)$

The dummy variable, y , was observed and was determined by y^* as follows

$$y = \{1 \text{ if } y^* > 0, 0 \text{ otherwise}\} \quad \dots (2)$$

The point of interest relates to the probability that y equals one. From the above equations, we see that:

$$\text{Prob}(y = 1) = \text{Prob}\left(\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_x X_k + \varepsilon > 0\right)$$

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$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{Prob}(\varepsilon > -\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_x X_k) \\ &= 1 - \Phi\left(-\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_x X_k\right) \end{aligned} \quad \dots (3)$$

Where Φ was the cumulative distribution function of ε (Liao)

The probit model assumed that the data were generated from a random sample of size N with a sample observation denoted by i , $i = 1, \dots, N$. Thus, the observations of y must be statistically independent of each other to rule out serial correlation. Additionally, it was assumed that the independent variables were random variables.

The Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) technique was used to estimate probit model parameters. MLE focused on choosing parameter estimates that gave the highest probability or likelihood of obtaining the observed sample y . The main principle of MLE was to choose as an estimate of β the set of K numbers that would maximize the likelihood of having observed this particularly (Aldrich and Nelson).

The specification of the probit model was as follows

$$Y^*_{ki} = \beta_{k0} + \beta_{k1} X_1 + \beta_{k2} X_2 + \beta_{k3} X_3 + \beta_{k4} X_4 + \beta_{k5} X_5 + \beta_{k6} X_6 + \beta_{k7} X_7 + \beta_{k8} X_8 + \beta_{k9} X_9 + \beta_{k10} X_{10} + \beta_{k11} X_{11} + \beta_{k12} X_{12} + \varepsilon \quad \dots (4)$$

Where,

Y = Use of the crop advisory model

X_1 to X_3 = Age parameters (Completed years)

X_4 to X_6 = Income parameters of the respondents

X_7 to X_9 = Farm Size parameters of the respondents

X_4 = Level of education (No. of formal years of education)

X_5 = Gender of the respondent

X_6 = Cropping pattern type

X_7 = Respondent membership in an organization (1 if yes, 0 otherwise)

X_8 = Agriculture is main occupation

In equation (4) Y^*_{ki} is a variable reflecting the willingness to use the crop advisory model by the i^{th} farmer with k denoting the adoption ($k = 0, 1$). if k is 0 then farmer is not ready to use the crop advisory model and if k is 1 then farmer is ready to use the crop advisory model. The age, education and farm size are categorized into three groups based on the quarters such as, up to first quarter, second to third quarter and above third quarter, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Farmer perceptions regarding a need for crop advisory

In order to understand farmers willingness towards the new evolution in the crop advisory systems. The sources of information for crop decision-making and willingness to use crop advisory services were assessed, they vary significantly across different farm sizes, as shown in Table 1. Small farmers predominantly rely on their own intuition, with 34.48 per cent of those willing (W) and 20.83 person of those not willing (NW) to use crop advisory services favouring this method. Neighbour suggestions are also important, with 27.59 per cent of

willing and 8.33 per cent of not willing small farmers relying on this source. SMS advisory was less commonly used among small farmers but shows a slightly higher uptake among those not willing to adopt crop advisory (12.50 %) than those willing (6.90 %), while naïve (farmers are mostly cultivating for the purpose of consumption and cultivate in only kharif season) numbers indicate most of the farmers were not willing (58.33 %) and rest were willing to use the new and latest advisory system for higher returns and benefits.

For medium farmers, own intuition remains a major source, especially for those willing to use crop advisory services (41.48 %). Neighbour suggestions are also significant, with 17.65 per cent of willing and 45.45 per cent of not willing medium farmers using this method. SMS advisory has moderate usage, with 17.65 per cent of willing and 18.18 per cent of not willing medium farmers using it, while naïve approaches are minimal, being used by only 14.29 per cent of willing medium farmers and none of the unwilling. The farmers in the region has adamant perception on the advisory systems, which being the major factor not willing to accept the new advisory system. The survey has also signified that farmers in the study area were hungry for the market and production development information indicating the need for the crop advisory. Hence, perception change process can help the farmers to accept the new crop advisory system.

In the case of large farmers, SMS advisory becomes more prominent, particularly among those not willing to use crop advisory services, where it accounts for 58.33 per cent. Among those willing to adopt advisory services, own intuition is still higher (42.86 %), with lower reliance on neighbour suggestions and naïve methods.

Factors influencing adoption of crop advisory services

In examining factors that influence farmers' choices in crop advisory, a probit model was employed with variables representing key demographic and farm characteristics. The Table 2 outlines the variables considered in the probit model to examine factors influencing farmers' decisions to adopt crop advisory services. The variables include demographics, socio-economic characteristics, farming practices, and external influences. Each variable is categorized into discrete groups or binary values, as follows:

Farmers were classified into four age groups: 18-30, 31-40, 41-55, and over 55. These groupings allow for assessing the influence of different life stages on the likelihood of accepting crop advisories. Younger farmers may be more open to adopting new practices, while older ones may rely more on traditional methods. Farmers' income levels are divided into four brackets, ranging from below ₹10,500 to above ₹74,500. This segmentation examines the impact of economic stability on decision-making, with higher-income groups potentially more capable of adopting advisories due to better resources. The categorization into four groups reflects the scale of farming operations, from small (<0.96 hectares) to large (>5.10 hectares). Larger farms may require more structured advisory services, while smaller farms may focus on subsistence practices.

Education levels range from primary schooling to degree-level education. This variable investigates the role of knowledge and literacy in farmers' ability to understand and act on crop advisories. Higher education may correlate with a greater willingness to innovate. Gender was captured as a binary variable (1 for males, 2 for females) to assess differences in advisory adoption between male and female farmers. Gender disparities often reflect access to resources and decision-making power. This binary variable identifies whether the farmer practices diversified cropping (1) or mono-cropping (0). Diversified systems might show greater interest in advisories due to their complexity. Membership in a farmer group (1) or absence thereof (0) is included to analyze how social networks influence acceptance of advisories. This binary variable distinguishes farmers who rely on agriculture as their primary occupation (1) from those who have a subsidiary source of income (0), highlighting the importance of agriculture in their livelihood.

Probit model estimates

The probit model in Table 3 revealed key factors that influenced farmers' acceptance of crop advisories. Age had a significant negative impact, with older farmers (31–40 and >55 years) being less likely to adopt advisories compared to younger ones (18–30 years), likely due to their reliance on traditional practices and resistance to change. Education played a crucial role, as farmers with a degree or higher were significantly more likely to accept advisories, reflecting their better understanding of the benefits of scientific farming methods, while those with lower education levels showed less inclination. Male farmers were more likely to adopt advisories than female farmers, potentially due to disparities in access to resources and decision-making roles. Diversified cropping patterns also increased acceptance, as such systems required more tailored and technical guidance. In contrast, variables such as farm size, group membership, and occupation had no significant effect, indicating that these factors did not strongly influence advisory adoption. The model explained 35 per cent of the variation in acceptance, highlighting the importance of addressing age-related resistance, improving education, and reducing gender disparities to enhance the uptake of crop advisories.

Marginal effects of the factors on crop advisory.

The marginal effects results in the table 4 showed the extent to which each variable influenced the likelihood of farmers accepting crop advisories. Age had a negative impact, with older farmers (31–40, 41–55, and >55 years) reducing the probability of acceptance by three per cent, two per cent, and seven per cent, respectively, likely due to their preference for traditional farming methods. Education had a positive effect, with farmers possessing higher education levels (degree or above) increasing the likelihood by 11 per cent, reflecting their ability to understand and appreciate the value of advisories, while lower education levels (primary or high school) contributed only marginally (1 %). Farm size showed mixed effects; smaller farms slightly increased the probability of acceptance (1–2 %), while very large farms (>5.10 hectares) reduced it by three per cent, possibly due to reliance on established practices. Gender marginally increased acceptance by two per cent indicating that male farmers had slightly better access to resources and information. Diversified cropping patterns and group membership had notable positive effects, increasing the likelihood by six per cent and eight per cent, respectively, as these factors often necessitated more technical advice and collaboration. Occupation had a minimal impact (1 %), suggesting that whether farming was a primary or secondary activity did not strongly influence advisory adoption. The findings of marginal effects emphasized the importance of education, gender equity, and promoting diversified farming to enhance advisory acceptance.

Conclusion and Implications

In the implementation of crop advisory systems, a lot depends on the demographic, educational and farming characteristics of farmers. Farmers that are young, well educated, and practice crop rotation seem to have a higher tendency of using these services. The gender gap and significant resistance to change in older farmers stand out as formidable obstacles. There are ways to overcome these barriers by informing campaigns addressing specific gender issues and explaining the advantages of the advisory systems. As the results of this study suggest, the focus on the preferences of farmers in the development and distribution of agricultural innovation is a way to facilitate the adoption of sustainable practices and improve farm productivity in the region. The need based training and extension services will enhance the effectiveness of farmer decision making with respect to the crop advisory systems.

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Table 1: Sources of information for farmers crop decision and willingness to use crop advisory

(N = 100)

Farmer Use of Crop Advisory Source of decision making	Small			Medium			Large		
	W	NW	Total	W	NW	Total	W	NW	Total
Own Intuition	10 (34.48)	5 (20.83)	15 (28.30)	7 (41.48)	4 (36.36)	11 (39.29)	3 (42.86)	1 (8.33)	4 (21.05)
Neighbour suggestion	8 (27.59)	2 (8.33)	10 (18.87)	3 (17.65)	5 (45.45)	8 (28.57)	2 (28.57)	1 (8.33)	3 (15.79)
SMS Advisory	2 (6.90)	3 (12.50)	5 (17.86)	3 (17.65)	2 (18.18)	5 (17.86)	2 (28.57)	7 (58.33)	9 (47.37)
Naïve Farmer	9 (31.03)	14 (58.33)	23 (14.29)	4 (23.53)	0 (0.00)	4 (14.29)	0 (0.00)	3 (25.00)	3 (15.79)
Total	29	24	53	17	11	28	7	12	19

Note: Figures in the parentheses indicates percentage totals.

W = Willingness to use and NW = Not willingness to use.

Table 2: Description of the variables used in probit model influencing the choice of crop advisory

Variables	Dummy allotment	Variable Description
Age	1	18-30
	2	31-40
	3	41-55
	4	>55
Income	1	<10,500
	2	10,500-44,500
	3	44,500-74,500
	4	>74,500
Farm Size	1	<0.96
	2	0.96-3.00
	3	3.01- 5.10
	4	>5.10
Education	1	Primary
	2	High school
	3	PUC
	4	Degree and Above
Gender	1	Male
	2	Female
Cropping Pattern	1	Diversified
	0	Mono cropping
Group Membership	1	Yes
	0	No
Occupation	1	Agriculture
	0	Subsidiary

Table 3: Estimates of probit model on factors influencing the farmers acceptance on crop advisory

Variable	Parameter	Co-efficient	P> z
constant	β_0	0.38	0.06
Age 2	β_1	-0.34	0.00
Age 3	β_2	-0.15	0.23
Age 4	β_3	-0.64	0.00
Education 2	β_4	0.08	0.38
Education 3	β_5	0.11	0.18
Education 4	β_6	0.33	0.00
Farm size 2	β_7	0.10	0.41
Farm size 3	β_8	0.16	0.36
Farm size 4	β_9	-0.24	0.15
Gender	β_{10}	0.30	0.00
Cropping pattern	β_{11}	0.13	0.05
Gross membership	β_{12}	0.19	0.25
Occupation	β_{13}	0.05	0.35
Pseudo r^2		0.35	

Table 4: Marginal effects of factors influencing the farmers acceptance on crop advisory.

Variable	Marginal effect
Age 2	-0.03
Age 3	-0.02
Age 4	-0.07
Education 2	0.01
Education 3	0.01
Education 4	0.11
Farm size 2	0.01
Farm size 3	0.02
Farm size 4	-0.03
Gender	0.02
Cropping pattern	0.06
Gross membership	0.08
Occupation	0.01